

Policy steps to unlock Agroforestry's Carbon Dioxide Removal potential

Based on consultations with stakeholders and experts in the trinational Upper Rhine Region during 2022 and 2023, this brief outlines key actions to scale agroforestry in Germany.

Key actions:

- Remove legal and administrative barriers
- Expand knowledge exchange and demonstration networks
- Increase financial incentives and advisory services
- Make carbon farming work for agroforestry

Germany aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2045 and to reduce net emissions from the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) sector to -25 MtCO₂e by 2030. Given that [the LULUCF sector remains a net emitter and there are persistent residual emissions from the German agriculture sector](#), restoring the sector's carbon sink capacity is essential in order to achieve both national and EU climate targets.

Agroforestry is a promising land-based carbon dioxide removal (CDR) approach, with the capacity to sequester carbon both above and below ground, going beyond soil organic carbon. Its integration of woody perennials into agricultural landscapes can generate [a range of co-benefits](#), including improved soil fertility, regulation of water quality, enhanced biodiversity, and increased productivity. Agroforestry is acknowledged in Germany's Climate Protection Law and supported by several EU policy frameworks, such as the Biodiversity Strategy, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the Forest Strategy. While it is also incorporated into the EU's Carbon Removals Carbon Farming (CRCF) regulation, it is not explicitly referenced in Germany's [guidelines to the Long-Term Strategy on Negative Emissions](#) yet.

To unlock agroforestry's CDR potential, agroforestry must be both desirable and feasible. This involves reversing decades-long policy trend towards the removal of trees, shrubs and hedges to 'make room' for mechanisation and intensification. [4] In 2023–27, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) allows additional financial support for modern agroforestry under Eco-Scheme No. 3. German states (Länder) can also support agroforestry through Pillar 2 rural development measures, so-called agri-environment-climate measures.

Some German states offer co-financing and technical support for agroforestry establishment. For instance, Mecklenburg-Vorpommern covers up to 65% of establishment costs, while Baden-Württemberg focuses its support on technical assistance. However, overall uptake remains low across Germany, with only a modest upward trend.

In 2024, [just 86 farms registered 170 hectares under Eco-Scheme No. 3](#) - far below the initial planned value of 200,000 hectares. It remains unclear, which policy adjustments are needed to make agroforestry more desirable and feasible.

Remove legal and administrative barriers

Legal uncertainty, particularly in protected areas, poses a significant obstacle to the adoption of agroforestry. Many farmers are concerned that systems which currently meet the definition of agroforestry in §4 of the CAP Direct Payments Regulation (GAPDZV) may be reclassified as biotopes (if not well maintained) or come under other protective regulations. This risk is already high for meadow orchards (Streuobstwiesen) in certain federal states. Hedgerows do not even meet the §4 definition and are already well protected under existing legislation throughout Germany. Such reclassification prevents the conversion of agroforests back into arable land.

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In order to ensure legal certainty, policymakers must better align the framework conditions for agricultural subsidies with nature conservation laws and provide the competent authorities with clear, uniform guidelines. In doing so, policymakers should consider expanding Section 14(2) of the Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG) to explicitly include agroforestry. This would ensure that agroforestry is not legally classified as an encroachment on nature and the landscape.

In 2020, [60.1% of Germany's agricultural land was leased](#). Thus, short-term and restrictive leases hinder long-term agroforestry investments. Most leases prohibit permanent plantings or require land to be returned in its original state. Introducing longer minimum lease terms and a right of first refusal - modelled on French policy - would reduce risk. Land consolidation could also support adoption in fragmented landscapes.

Expand knowledge exchange and demonstration networks

Knowledge gaps remain a key barrier to agroforestry adoption. While many farmers are aware of the effects of climate change, some lack the practical knowledge or conviction to implement agroforestry systems.

To close this gap, policymakers should support peer learning and regional demonstration networks. Disseminating successful business models and highlighting additional ecological benefits could improve perceptions of agroforestry and promote its acceptance. This could be achieved through training courses and field days led by experienced agroforestry practitioners, for example. This is particularly important in regions under high environmental pressure, such as [Schleswig-Holstein](#). Mutual exchange also promotes the development of value chains and distribution channels beyond direct marketing.

In order to close knowledge gaps between farmers and civil servants, agroforestry should be incorporated into agricultural and forestry education programmes. Highlighting viable business models that extend beyond subsidies can foster long-term acceptance.

Increase financial incentives and advisory services

Financial incentives remain key alongside technical assistance. Upfront payments can compensate for additional investment costs, while financial support for maintenance can offset income losses during the initial stages of adopting agroforestry - provided that it proves to be more profitable than conventional agriculture in the long term. An alternative to upfront payments is material support, such as free seedlings or fencing. [3]

When deciding on the level of support for agroforestry, policymakers should recognise that agroforestry represents a paradigm shift from land expansion and specialisation to vertical scaling and diversification, and from machine-oriented to labour-oriented practices. Relatively successful support schemes in Germany's [Black Forest Centre/North Nature Park agroforestry pilot project](#), and in France's [Let's Plant Hedges! \(Plantons des haies!\)](#) and [Green and Blue Infrastructure \(Trame Verte et Bleue\)](#) programmes (see also [project example](#)), demonstrate the potential of this instrument to facilitate this shift if it is well designed, combined with other interventions, and embedded in an enabling policy.

Stakeholders have agreed that the current eco-scheme payment of €200 per hectare is insufficient and does not reflect the diversity of agroforestry systems, and it was noted elsewhere that actual opportunity costs of agroforestry were [underestimated](#) when designing the payment. Consequently, a payment increase to €600/ha has been approved for 2026 onwards. This means 90€ per year for an agroforestry system with 15% of ground area occupied with woody area.

In addition, [interest groups noted](#) that the calculation of eco-scheme 3 deliberately did not take into account investment costs for agroforestry, which [prompted a broad green alliance](#) to recommend that investment subsidies be designed as follows:

- Eligibility for all investment costs,
- 100% compensation for the first 10 hectares,
- 80% compensation for the next 10 hectares,
- 50% compensation for any additional hectares.

Several differences can be noted when comparing the existing investment support schemes offered by the German states (see box) with the alliance's recommendations. One significant issue is the GAK requirement for farmers to co-finance investments and the imposition of funding limits, despite EU Regulation 2021/2115

(Art. 73 (4)(c)), which permits full funding for agroforestry establishment. Furthermore, initial experiences with Bavaria's investment support scheme suggest that farmers' own service work should be recognised as eligible expenditure. [5]

The policy landscape is further complicated by Agri-Environment-Climate Measures (AECMs) under the Rural Development Plans, which support agroforestry but differ significantly in design and eligibility criteria across regions. From a farmer's perspective, harmonising fragmented funding schemes, streamlining administrative processes, and allowing more flexible agroforestry designs would greatly improve accessibility and uptake.

Greater flexibility could be achieved by removing caps on woody cover and permitting crop diversity between tree rows - both of which currently exclude innovative agroforestry systems. Additional restrictions on forest pastures further limit viable options. [2] Policymakers should revise the eligibility criteria and more consistently recognise agroforestry as a compensatory measure for construction impacts or as an alternative to clearing overgrown forest on former agricultural land.

Carbon farming and certification

Voluntary carbon markets could be a useful complement to public subsidies for agroforestry. The EU's CRCF regulation, in force since December 2024, aims to regulate these markets in response to

growing private sector demand for high-quality CDR certificates to achieve net-zero targets. In the long term, this could be the first step towards integrating the LULUCF sector into the EU Emissions Trading System. A [CDR calculation methodology for agroforestry and soil carbon](#) is expected to be finalised in 2025, with certification of eligible activities set to begin in 2026. In parallel, a consortium is working on a German [DIN standard](#) for quantifiable, additional, long-term and sustainable CO₂ storage in agroforestry systems and products.

While the CRCF presents new opportunities for agroforestry, its overall impact remains uncertain. The EU's ambitious LULUCF target of -310 MtCO₂e per year by 2030, alongside restrictions under the proposed Green Claims Directive, could limit the supply of certified removals for voluntary market use.

To unlock the potential of carbon farming for agroforestry, policymakers should align CRCF and CAP rules, ensure a simple and robust regulatory framework and invest in farmer capacity including the promotion of viable agroforestry carbon business models. [Lessons from past failures in international carbon markets](#) must be taken into account. Particular attention must be paid to desirability of the framework's effects on smallholders and their ongoing structural crowding out as well as on more complex, small-scale and diverse agroforestry systems.

About CDR-PoEt (2021 - 2025)

Carbon Dioxide Removals – Policies and Ethics (CDR-PoEt) examines the ethical and equity implications of policy instruments for CDR, based on interdisciplinary research and stakeholder deliberations. The project specifically evaluates the feasibility ('what can we do from an economic, socio-cultural, and institutional perspective?') and the desirability ('what do we want to do?') of CDR policies and methods in their specific contexts, providing a foundation for developing policy recommendations at local, national and international levels.

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